

The Santa Catarina industry: advances and setbacks in the 21st century

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Abstract

The neoliberal counterrevolution that began at the end of the 20th century triggered a blockade of industrialization in Brazil, resulting, in this first quarter of the 21st century, in the strangulation of various industrial sectors. Combined in part with the denationalization of the economy promoted by the unplanned trade liberalization of the Collor (1990–1992) and FHC (1995–2002) administrations, the process of deindustrialization has become a pressing issue, challenging Brazilian intellectuals to seek concrete alternatives for the resumption of economic and social development. However, deindustrialization as a theme within the regional question in Southern Brazil is still presented in a rather incipient way. In this regard, this work seeks to contribute to the deepening of regional studies in the state of Santa Catarina, especially considering that some of its most industrialized regions — such as the Itajaí Valley and Northeastern Santa Catarina — have managed (some industrial branches) to resist this process. It appears that the industrial dynamism of this regional social formation is closely linked to the role of small-scale commodity production, initially deciphered by A. Mamigonian (1960, 1965, 1986, 2011) and corroborated by Barros de Castro (1985). The self-made man condition, brought by immigrant settlers who, at first, presented themselves as “capitalists without capital”, later enabled the transition from craftsmanship to industry, triggering particularities in the process that were not fully captured by regional scholars such as P. Singer. Furthermore, in addition to import substitution policies — diametrically opposed to the Schumpeterian entrepreneur's vision — the rise of Santa Catarina's industrial capital to state power ensured, over the past four decades (1980–2020), sustained economic growth, often above the national average, even though some manufacturing segments were penalized by predatory imports.

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1. Introduction

The industrial sector can be considered an eminently geographical phenomenon, with the particularity of being complex, as it operates directly within an intricate network of relationships that transcend segmentation. It constitutes a formidable analytical standpoint for identifying spatial dynamics, since it emerges as the product of converging forces emanating from a broad spatial framework, usually subordinated to national and international structures. The sector encompasses a diverse network of relationships and is rich in spatial and structural qualities.

As Milton Santos (1977) taught, by identifying three main scales of geographical analysis — the global, national, and regional-local levels — it is with such breadth that this phenomenon must be investigated. It is worth noting that it remains a reality undergoing profound transformation at the beginning of the twenty-first century.

According to A. Mamigonian (2025), in Brazil, the last four decades have shown a loss of momentum and fragmentation of the industrial sector, which accounted for around 30% of the national GDP in the 1980s and currently represents one of the major bottlenecks to be addressed, as the economy becomes increasingly internationally competitive due to the ongoing “market wars.”

In any case, the industry of Santa Catarina appears to have reacted to the adversities of Brazilian deindustrialization; however, it can be said that some of its industrial sectors have been severely constrained. In this sense, the objective of this study is to identify, through a systemic view of national and regional realities, the deficiencies and potentialities that currently characterize the structure of Santa Catarina’s industrial base, as well as the conjunctural obstacles posed by recent transformations in the international division of labor, which extend beyond the borders of the nation-state.

To this end, this study is divided into three sections. The first presents the method, anchored in the Marxist category of socioeconomic formation, which guides studies in economic geography. The second provides a review of the literature that informs the research on the industrialization and deindustrialization of the state of Santa Catarina. Finally, the third section offers a historical overview of the process under study, followed by the concluding remarks.

2. On Method: Geography and the Category of Socioeconomic Formation

Breaking with the theoretical–methodological currents in economic geography that do not articulate theory and praxis - that is, the relationship between the State [territory] and the politics of spectacle [society], while neglecting the objectivity of both in the development of a given socio-spatial formation, as noted by Milton Santos (1977) - this research in progress has sought to investigate the recent transformations in the most industrialized regions of the state of Santa Catarina, namely the Itajaí Valley and the northeastern part of the state.

Indeed, it is important to recall the warnings of Marx, who, in the preface to the first edition of *Capital*, drew attention to the abandonment of “disinterested inquiry” by the “mercenary swordsmen,” who replaced “impartial scientific investigation” with bad faith - that is, with “apologetic intentions” (Marx, 2017, p.86). Similarly, Antonio Gramsci (2005), in his letters, emphasized that scientists are always “disinterested” (Gramsci, 2005, p.179) and criticized the sordidly “Jewish” conception that regards “theoretical behavior as authentically human” yet fails to understand praxis, since it “is only apprehended and fixed in its... dirty form.” In other words, these authors are endorsing the rigor of the historical materialist method and its infinite possibilities for combining the two paths of transition to capitalism (revolutionary or Prussian), as indicated by Lenin (1977; 1980; 1985) - approaches that are, so to speak, close to the historical-genetic method of A. Cholley (1964) applied in geographical studies, within which this research is situated.

Within this framework of geographical thought, the theme of industrialization, as addressed by Brazilian geography, has received considerable attention throughout the 20th century, gaining momentum from the 1950s onward with the emergence of the new dynamic center of the Brazilian economy, as identified by Celso Furtado (1959) in *The Economic Formation of Brazil*. During this period, Brazil increasingly internalized the rhythm of accumulation of its endogenous cycle - coined by Ignacio Rangel (1980) as the “Brazilian Juglar cycles” - thus consolidating the well-known process of import-substitution industrialization widely promoted by the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC) (Bielschowsky, 1996).

In this context, the pioneering role of Brazilian geographers is well known, such as the Paulista scholars Pasquale Petrone, in *As indústrias paulistas e os fatores de sua expansão*, and D. Lino de Mattos, with works like *Os fatores da industrialização de São Paulo* (1957) and *O Parque Industrial Paulistano* (1958), who - long before sociologists and economists - were already prominent in studies of industrialization, emphasizing the fundamental role of immigrants in predominantly industrial initiatives, later corroborated by Bresser Pereira (1964).

From the 1960s onward, the continuity of studies on Brazil’s industrialization process was taken up by geographer Armen Mamigonian (1986), who further developed the analysis of the role of small-scale commodity production, previously highlighted by Pierre Monbeig in *Pioneiros e Fazendeiros de São Paulo* (1998) and *As Estruturas Agrárias da Faixa Pioneira Paulista* (1953), as well as by L. Waibel in *As Zonas Pioneiras no Brasil* (1955). These studies sought to decipher the factors that led to the genesis and development of capitalism in the country.

From this perspective, Mamigonian was able to devise a research agenda on industry in Southern Brazil, recognizing that the primitive accumulation that spread through pioneer areas—triggering “a development of commercial and industrial functions, both in regional capitals and in the new settlements” (Monbeig, 1984,

p.347)—resembled the conditions of the self-made man brought by immigrants, who in most cases were “capitalists without capital,” gradually integrating into local, regional, and later national markets.

Since 1958, with the publication of the pioneering Atlas of Santa Catarina, organized by Carlos Augusto de Figueiredo Monteiro, Mamigonian - expanding on Peluso Jr.’s considerations in *Tradição e Plano Urbano* - identified the first social differentiations of industrialization from the perspective of “habitat,” resulting from both Azorean and German colonization. The latter gave rise to industrial development from the D. Francisca Colony (1851), organized by the *Kolonisationsverein von Hamburg*, as well as the Blumenau Colony (1850), in the mid-Itajaí-Açu Valley.

This, in turn, led to a series of subsequent studies, such as the chapter on Industry in the Atlas of Santa Catarina (1986), where Mamigonian explained, using the dialectical historical-genetic method proposed by André Cholley (1964), the industrialization of Santa Catarina: not all industry originated from handicrafts, nor did all handicrafts evolve into industry, but rather from the role of small-scale commodity production. Later, he sought to understand the phenomena that led to the paradox of the “dynamism/strangulation” binomial, since - even though the overall industrial landscape in Santa Catarina continued to grow above the national average - there were a series of bottlenecks in key industrial sectors that suffered the consequences of the neoliberal policies promoted by the unplanned trade liberalization of the 1990s.

3. Literature Review³

Once in Paraíba, in August 1991, a seminar was organized around the ideas of Celso Furtado⁴, which included the participation of Ignacio Rangel in the second panel — “Exile in France, the return to Brazil; from the Ministry of Culture to the present day (1964–1990)”. On that occasion, when the floor was opened for debate, Rangel expressed deep dissatisfaction with the poor synthesis reached during that meeting, as noted in the account by Corrêa (2008, p.94).

“ — Rossini, I’m worried. People are thinking about Brazil all wrong! And it’s coming from people in positions of responsibility! I’m going to ask Arraes for fifteen minutes to clear up these misconceptions and turn the table”.

However, his request was denied three times by Arraes, who argued that at any moment “Deputy Ulysses Guimarães would arrive for the closing ceremony of the

³ This article is the result of some updates to two previously published works in Portuguese: “A indústria de Santa Catarina: dinamismo e estrangulamento,” in *Santa Catarina: Estudos de Geografia Econômica e Social*. Florianópolis: GCN/UFSC, 2011, and “Brasil hoje e amanhã na divisão planificada do trabalho,” *Revista Ciência Geográfica*, v. 27, p. 2658–2694, 2024. These works are currently being revised and updated to be included in fascicle 5 of the *Geographic Atlas of Santa Catarina*, scheduled for publication in 2026.

⁴ For more information about the seminar and the panelists presentations, see “Era da Esperança: Teoria e Política no Pensamento de Celso Furtado” (Orgs.) GAUDÊNCIO, F. de S.; FORMIGA, M.). São Paulo: Paz e Terra, 1995.

seminar.” In the meantime, Rangel turned to Rossini and said: “– After all, who exactly is this Ulysses Guimarães they keep talking about, Rossini!?” (Corrêa, 2008, p.94).

More than three decades after the seminar, Rangel’s words remain relevant when we observe how people still have a flawed understanding of the country — even the most worn-out analyses of intellectuals who try to treat Brazilian deindustrialization as an epiphenomenon, similar to the issue of inflation. Currently, both the orthodox and heterodox economic schools continue insisting on the universalization of partial diagnoses, whose therapeutic approaches to the diffuse problems of economic and social development end up narrowing their causes into a compartmentalized worldview, therefore close to the concept *ruse*⁵.

Well, the so-called hypothesis of Brazilian deindustrialization should be framed in other terms, that is, substantiated based on the inter-imperialist rivalries that forcibly led Latin America and Africa to open their markets without any effective planning measures from the 1990s onward. After all, without presupposing planning techniques as an essential tool for the resumption of development, the debate will continue to be habitually redundant, revolving around disputes over concepts and classifications. Those who omit political science in economic studies forget that politics is nothing more than “economics carried out by other means,” just as war is “politics carried out by other means,” that is, “by violent means, Lenin would add” (Rangel, 1982, p.25). This means that the

Conflicts that find no resolution in their original field, which is basically the economic one, tend to involve social classes internally and peoples on the international stage; in other words, they tend to shift to the political arena where, eventually, a solution may be found. However, if this does not occur, the human conflict will either regress to the economic field or escalate to the military one. Thus, the fundamental conflicts of interest raised by the current global economic crisis of capitalism take the form of political conflict (Rangel, 1982, p.26).

In this sense, if one does not take into account the context of the neoliberal counterrevolution imposed by the aggressiveness of imperialism since the 1980s—under R. Reagan and M. Thatcher—and its multiple consequences in the deceleration of the Brazilian economy up to the present day, it becomes practically impossible—if not an assault on reason—to seek comparative parameters with

⁵ The recurring literature on the process of Brazilian deindustrialization, as pointed out by Morceiro (2012), is limited to three groups of approaches (employment, production — value added, and foreign trade performance), in which the variables sometimes appear combined and sometimes not. According to the author, there is no consensus among the approaches, either regarding the definition of the concept—since the variables are fixed according to the researcher’s discretion—or regarding the conclusion about whether deindustrialization has occurred in Brazil. For some, who combined the three variables in their analyses, there was no deindustrialization in Brazil, as is the case of Coriat, who, “from the perspective of employment,” observed that the numbers remained at balanced levels. For others, such as Oreiro, Bresser-Pereira, Cano, among others, the loss of share in the other two variables (foreign trade and value added) confirms the hypothesis of deindustrialization.

developed or developing countries that have taken (and are still taking) economic planning to its ultimate consequences, as is the case of South Korea, Singapore, Indonesia, India, China, among others.

According to Rangel (1990), Brazil, up until the late 1980s, had still embraced—albeit somewhat naively—the ideas of economic planning, since both the right and the left of the political spectrum desired development and industrialization, thus moving “in the generally desired direction, though not at the desired pace”, by responding wisely to crises and recessions through foreign exchange policies, state investment, and the very implementation of labor rights.

However, in the 1990s, the foundational principles of planning were abandoned—along with them, the possibility of a “review of concession rights,” which had been the starting point for combating recession by creating jobs, demand, and income in underinvested sectors. Privatizations of public utility services were carried out through the conversion of external debt, without the capacity to stimulate productive capacity, leading to a deep form of dumping in the national economy (Rangel, 1990). Furthermore, the dismantling of the market reserve policy blocked the possibility of a planned approach to economic opening, which, in practice, would have been implemented through foreign trade—where Brazil would open up in a planned way to countries that purchased its products, thereby guaranteeing a reciprocal market for the goods of both partners (Rangel, 1991).

Nevertheless, throughout this period, little to no attention was given to the resumption of economic planning by the so-called “progressive” intelligentsia, including the so-called new developmentalists. Even though they deserve credit for denouncing harmful macroeconomic policies (exchange rate, interest rates, unemployment, Central Bank autonomy, etc.) imposed by the IMF and similar institutions, they continue to diagnose the problem of industrialization—or, as they put it, deindustrialization—by treating “industry as a single homogeneous whole” (Morceiro, 2018, p.137).

On the other hand, the recent studies by Morceiro (2018, p.131) have made a unique contribution to the discussion of measures through which the principles of planning for Brazilian foreign trade could be structured based on the import agenda, as proposed by Ignacio Rangel. This is due to the study’s in-depth sectoral analysis of national industry, its varying degrees of deindustrialization, productive densification, and integration into global value chains, as well as the “import coefficient of tradable inputs and components” (CIICC). The results of the research are revealing, as there is no uniformity in the process of Brazilian deindustrialization, as

First, Brazilian manufacturing experienced a significant decline in productive densification during the decade of the 21st century that saw the highest industrial growth since the 1970s. However, this setback in densification did not lead to an absolute deindustrialization of

industrial sectors, as these did not show a decrease in employment related to industrial operations (Morceiro, 2020, p.856).

Shifting to the regional scale, Rosa (2023, p.83), in a recent study on deindustrialization in the state of Santa Catarina over the past four decades, points to evidence that the degree of deindustrialization in the state's economy was lower during the first decade of the 21st century, with a "specialization in the export of products from the food, beverage, and tobacco industries". However, from 2010 onward, there was a "deterioration of trade balances alongside a re-primarization of the productive structure," with the export profile becoming restricted to medium- and low-tech intensity products, accounting for approximately 70% of total exports.

In light of the current state of Brazilian and Santa Catarina's industry, it is possible to say that - contrary to pessimistic analyses - Brazil still possesses considerable industrial capacity, ready to support renewed growth. This would only require that industrial and macroeconomic policies be based on the "science of planning" - a *sine qua non* condition both for the capitalist world, which increasingly needs to plan its foreign trade (Moré Ramos, 2024), and for the socialist world itself, under the leadership of Chinese economic planning, which has, in fact, demonstrated prudence in positioning itself above good and evil -unlike Soviet planning, which did not adjust adequately to Kondratiev's economic cycles (Ramos and Bastos, 2023).

In fact, if the studies by Morceiro (2020) have the merit of pointing to the possibility of planning our foreign trade based on sectors where import coefficients have become predatory to domestic industry - as does Rosa (2023), in the case of Santa Catarina - it is important to emphasize that these studies remain within the scope of a literature that explains the deindustrialization process purely through an economic-structural lens. They lack a broader, integrated vision that considers the complexity of the economic-social formations involved - a perspective insisted upon here, particularly in the regional case of Santa Catarina. This is necessary to avoid repeating the mistakes of the "technological backwardness" narrative used to explain Brazil's crisis in the 1980s, which influenced everything "from scientific reports (Luciano Coutinho – Unicamp) to the President of the Republic" (Mamigonian, 1999, p.160).

Indeed, for Morceiro and Tessarin (2019, p.18), what matters in explaining Brazilian deindustrialization is to frame it comparatively alongside the deindustrialization of the United States and to label it as "premature" whereas the U.S. process has been occurring "naturally" since the 1970s. This is justified on the basis that the two countries "share similarities, as both are populous, continental nations, rich in natural resources, were former colonies, and experienced periods of slavery".

There is no doubt that the two countries share some similarities. However, strictly speaking, from their origins and throughout their development, Brazil and the

United States have far more differences than common denominators⁶. A fundamental divergence lies in the neoliberal counterrevolution imposed by the United States on Brazil in the late 1980s—precisely when strategic sectors of what had been the most dynamic industrial economy in the Western capitalist world between 1930 and 1980 (Mamigonian, 2021) began to fall under the control of foreign firms through a brutal wave of mergers and acquisitions (Corrêa, 2004).

In any case, this is not the place to delve deeply into such comparative issues. What should be said is that if economists like Morceiro (2020), Rosa (2023), among others, do not lose sight of the industrialization process in Brazil and Santa Catarina as a whole, and if they continue organizing—with the same capacity and competence—the evidence pointing to the non-homogeneity of the national industrial fabric under the effects of deindustrialization, then there is no doubt that the “science of planning” in Brazil will have the conditions to be resumed and guided in alignment with the economic cycles that Ignacio Rangel systematically emphasized in the process of import-substitution industrialization throughout the 20th century (Ramos and Bastos, 2021).

3.1. Interpretations of industrialization in Santa Catarina

There is now no doubt in the current literature that Santa Catarina undertook a significant industrial effort dating back to its origins in the late 19th century. The first textile industries emerged around 1880, such as Hering in Blumenau, and they had to overcome numerous difficulties. However, from 1930 to 1980, with several sectors established, Santa Catarina’s industry experienced enormous expansion, with many regions successfully integrating into both national and international markets. This was the case of the Itajaí Valley, where the world’s second-largest textile and garment cluster was created in the 1970s.

After this period, much to the surprise of many observers, Santa Catarina’s industry, like the national industry as a whole, was subjected in the 1990s to a unilateral and destructive trade liberalization, which worsened from 2005 onward, with a strong tendency toward deindustrialization (Oreiro e Feijó, 2010). Therefore, interpreters should take into account the various interests at play and attempt the closest possible approximation to reality—ranging from deciphering the origins and evolution of the

⁶ The recent work published by Rocha and Vieira (2021) is enlightening regarding the genesis and evolution of Brazil and the USA, revealing, for example, in addition to their geographical, economic, political, cultural peculiarities that gave rise to the revolutionary path (small-scale mercantile production) as the primary engine of capitalist accumulation, the role of the marriage between banks and industry in the United States at the end of the 19th century. This union ultimately gave rise to an early national financial capitalism which, while it financed Brazilian industrialization until the 1980s, reacted—similarly to English industrial capitalism in the 19th century—by interrupting the emergence of Brazilian industrial capitalism, blocking the fusion of our banks with our own industry and the development of national financial capitalism.

industrial process to understanding the characteristics of the crisis of the 1990s, which persist to this day. Let us then try to outline the main interpretations, their merits, and their weaknesses.

In the historiography of Santa Catarina during the 1930s and 1940s, the state's industrialization divided opinions: Marcos Konder, the intellectual of the powerful Konder oligarchy, stated around 1930 that he was opposed to “artificial” industries—those that swollen and polluted the cities—and preferred agro-industries, such as the Adelaide sugar mill in Itajaí, owned by his family. In fact, he was referring negatively to the neighboring cities of Blumenau and Brusque, whose industrialists began to rival the export-import merchants of the coastal cities. Marcos Konder's view aligned with the ideas of Eugênio Gudín, which still dominate economic thought at FGV and PUC Rio de Janeiro and remain hostile to industrialization to this day.

A few years later, Cabral (1994), considering the industrial cities successful, declared the failure of the German colonization of São Pedro de Alcântara, established in 1829 near the capital, arguing that it had not given rise to significant urban and industrial life. This was an evident mistake, as that colonization created popular wealth for thousands of settlers, expanding to the Itajaí Valley, Ilhota and Gaspar in the lower valley, Ituporanga in the upper valley near Rio do Sul, and also toward the south of the state, passing through Braço do Norte to Forquilha near Criciúma. It also produced intellectuals and politicians such as Felipe Schmidt, Lauro Muller, Evaristo Arns, Raulino Reitz, among others.

After Santa Catarina's intellectuals began to partially overcome the inferiority complex that the state was merely a “transit area between São Paulo and Rio Grande do Sul,” an exaggerated optimism about the state's industrialization emerged, with two almost euphoric positions: 1) adoption of the CEPAL perspective on the center-periphery relationship, promoted nationally by intellectuals such as C. Furtado and F. Oliveira, both leaders of SUDENE; and 2) adoption of a triumphalist stance regarding Schumpeterian entrepreneurs and the “Santa Catarina model of development.”

Both right-wing and left-wing intellectuals aligned with the first perspective. In the former case, F. Mattos (1968) insisted on the disadvantageous exchange relations between Santa Catarina and the rest of Brazil. Meanwhile, E. Silva (1978) and A. Souto (1980) highlighted the supply of industrial inputs (auto parts, for example) to São Paulo, the dynamic national center and location of the automotive industry at that time.

On the other hand, there was a triumphalist celebration of Santa Catarina's industrial successes with O. Bossle (1985), who, besides excessively valuing the export-import merchants, emphasized Santa Catarina's isolation at the beginning of industrialization. Like M.L. Renaux Hering (1987), O. Bossle also overestimated the role of entrepreneurs, but it is Bossle who is credited with the idea of the “Santa Catarina model of development,” which is also exaggerated.

It is interesting to note that all the authors of these two interpretative currents, to varying degrees, worked with empirical data, while a new interpreter, this time from the naive left, I. Michels (1998), rejected all previous interpretations: according to him, Santa Catarina's industrialization resulted from the overexploitation of workers and the support of the state government. The author seemed to forget that the same had happened in Puritan Revolution England, Bismarck's Germany, and Meiji Japan. He tried to apply, belatedly, to Santa Catarina the ideas of F.H. Cardoso, E. Falleto, and especially R.M. Marini about the inevitability of a fanciful socialist revolution. This was very late, as the Washington Consensus was already dismantling much of Santa Catarina's industrial park, with the endorsement of one of its inspirers.

Another curiosity, in this brief overview of interpretations, lies in the similarity between authors widely separated in time, such as P. Singer (1968) and those gathered by L. Mattei and H. Nunes Lins (2010). When analyzing the industrialization of Blumenau, Singer started from the idea of mode of production rather than socio-economic formation. Thus, he found many more similarities with São Paulo, Porto Alegre, Belo Horizonte, and Recife, emphasizing the economic surpluses obtained by merchant capital, when in reality, there are many specificities—otherwise it would be impossible to understand the loss of momentum in Recife and Rio de Janeiro, for example.

There is also a certain dogmatism in J.M. Cardoso de Mello (1975), who insisted on periodizing 1933–1955 as a time of “restricted industrialization,” as a consequence of foreign exchange scarcity that strangled imports of capital goods, without realizing that this was a period of strong industrial growth due to the many reproductions in mechanical workshops inside factories of the few machines that could be imported. These and other dogmatisms led the Santa Catarina authors to propose a periodization detached from reality: 1) 1880 to 1945, 2) 1945 to 1962, 3) 1962 to 1990, and 4) after 1990, underestimating, for example, the year 1930, when industrial import substitution gained enormous momentum in Santa Catarina, as in all of Brazil, through successive national Juglar cycles.

The two aforementioned interpretations took place under the aegis of CEPAL's (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean) thought, which commits some errors, such as overvaluing the recessionary fight against inflation, as occurred with the Triennial Plan in the 1960s and the “freeze policies” during the Sarney government, aligning itself with the monetarists from PUC-Rio de Janeiro—preliminaries for the Real Plan and its destructive exchange rate anchor in the 1990s. It should be noted, moreover, that among the social sciences, economics and sociology tend to overestimate their theories to the detriment of reality.

In Western Europe, capitalism arose from two paths: from large commercial capital (Flemish cities and Northern Italy) and from small-scale mercantile production in England and other countries. Similarly, in Western Europe, the starting point in Brazil

occurred at the end of the 19th century through the transformation of export-import merchants in port cities—from Belém and São Luís to Florianópolis and Rio Grande—into textile and food industry entrepreneurs, who, however, did not have much staying power, as they enjoyed privileges in the captive markets of their hinterlands. Entrepreneurs born out of small-scale production in the São Paulo coffee economy (mechanics, tinsmiths, shoemakers, etc.), in European-settled areas in Southern Brazil, the semi-arid Northeast, and so forth, emerged from the outset as competitive and without privileges from captive markets and thus soon stood out. Without idolizing or demonizing them, Santa Catarina's entrepreneurs resembled the Schumpeterian entrepreneurs of early 20th-century USA, such as H. Ford or T. Edison, for the reasons indicated. Or the Schumpeterian entrepreneurs from Silicon Valley in California, contemporary China, and other countries—such as the founders of Dígito, from Florianópolis, in recent years.

On the other hand, when the CEPAL scholars from Santa Catarina, analyzing the center-periphery relations, pointed to the inferiority of Santa Catarina compared to São Paulo, they perhaps did not know at the time that the multinational automakers (GM, Ford, Volkswagen) located in São Paulo were oligopolizing the domestic market and therefore not renewing themselves, but were imposing fierce competition among their national auto parts suppliers, making them increasingly competitive and, over time, exporters—as happened with the Tupy foundry in Joinville. The gap between São Paulo and Santa Catarina was narrowing. Since the 1980s, not only Santa Catarina but also Rio Grande do Sul and Paraná became part of the core of the Brazilian industrial system, led by São Paulo—something that interpreters of various perspectives ultimately failed to see.

However, the highly favorable conditions in Brazil from 1930 to 1980, such as the industrializing economic policies among others, worsened, and thus dynamic groups like Hering in Santa Catarina or Villares in São Paulo shrank or disappeared.

3.2. Brief history of the origins of industrialization in Santa Catarina

Around 1950, it was common to attribute the industrialization of southern Brazil to the region's artisanal wealth. But as J. Roche (1969) pointed out, not all southern industry was born from craftsmanship, nor did all craftsmanship turn into industry. In any case, the artisanal wealth of the German, Italian, and Polish settlement areas in southern Brazil constituted an important foundation in the industrial process, as in the case of mechanics, foundry workers, and electricians in the industrialization of Caxias do Sul and its surroundings (Abramo Eberle, Marcopolo, Tramontina, etc.) or Joinville, Jaraguá do Sul, Brusque, etc. (Consul, WEG, Schulz, Fischer, etc.).

It is interesting to note that the major merchants of Blumenau, Joinville, and Brusque, who accumulated far more resources than the small merchants of the colony-sale system or the affluent artisans and settlers, rarely ventured into industrial activities. The major yerba mate merchants in Joinville were pioneers in establishing the

regional electricity company, as was also the case with the major merchants of Blumenau, but not in actual factories. The largest merchant in Brusque, João Bauer, preferred to relocate to Rio do Sul, then a pioneering colonial zone.

Thus, the key point of the explanation lies in the type of society that was organized in the settlement areas and the social classes that composed it. It involved the establishment of thousands of small landowning farmers, many artisans, workers, and small merchants who already practiced a significant social division of labor in their European homelands. The settlers, besides salt, kerosene, and matches, bought fabrics, work tools, etc.

Many artisans and workers migrated after being expelled from Germany, Italy, and Poland in the second half of the 19th century, as a consequence of the industrial capitalism growth crises in those countries. For example, textile workers and artisans from Łódź (Poland), of German origin, settled in Brusque.

This small-scale mercantile production, reminiscent of the settlement of the northeastern United States, is a fundamental factor to understand the success of the industrialization of Novo Hamburgo and Caxias do Sul in Rio Grande do Sul, and Blumenau and Joinville in Santa Catarina. In this sense, speaking of a “Catarinense development model” seems restrictive to us, since the fundamental factor—the small-scale mercantile production transplanted from 19th-century Europe—occurred in the settlement areas of Rio Grande do Sul, Santa Catarina, and Paraná, and its industrial success contrasts with the weakness of industrialization in areas of extensive livestock farming (Campanha Gaúcha, Campos de Lages, etc.).

It should be said, in passing, that it is impossible to understand São Paulo’s industrialization without referring to the strength of small-scale mercantile production existing both inside and outside the coffee plantations, as case studies clearly show (Franca, Limeira, Piracicaba, etc.). Thus, the emphasis on the Schumpeterian interpretation (the role of entrepreneurs) also seems limited to us, since the multiplication of entrepreneurs cannot occur in a society based on pastoral latifundium-based with impoverished peasants.

As is known, Hering, Döhler, and Schlösser, master textile artisans, were forced to leave areas of rapid industrialization in Europe (Saxony, etc.) at the end of the 19th century, as crafts and small businesses were forced to close during periods of crisis. Upon settling in Blumenau, Joinville, and Brusque, respectively, they could rely on guaranteed buyers for their products—the local farmers—and commission carpenters to build manual wooden looms. However, they depended on scarce and difficult-to-obtain financial resources locally, which were gathered through various types of work, and on cotton threads imported from Europe through a well-established commercial intermediary apparatus in the main Brazilian port cities, especially Rio de Janeiro.

At the same time, during this global depression period (1873–1896), it should be noted that factory units, often textile, originated from commercial capital in Brazilian port cities such as Salvador, Recife, and Rio de Janeiro, with large scale from the start. Similarly, in southern Brazil, an early generation of industries linked to commercial capital emerged (Rio Grande, Porto Alegre, Florianópolis, Itajaí, etc.), and in the capital of Santa Catarina, the powerful commercial firm Hoepcke set up nail factories, a shipyard, and acquired a lace and embroidery factory. These industries, born from export-import commercial capital and generally privileged by geographic market reserves, suffered from the unification of the national market caused by the Revolution of 1930 and eventually disappeared.

Meanwhile, in the German-settled areas of Santa Catarina, industries started small and had to undergo a long local learning process of resilience and slow expansion. They were also favored by the international context of 1873–1896, which, besides creating a natural protectionist barrier due to foreign exchange scarcity, forced the Brazilian government to raise import tariffs. These industries maintained close commercial relations with Germany, updating techniques and importing more advanced machinery. Their growth was slow but steady, allowing them to reach, even before World War I, the markets of southern Brazil as well as São Paulo and Rio de Janeiro. The success of these first textile industries in Santa Catarina, especially in Blumenau, led to the creation of new, initially small textile companies such as Teka, Altenburg, Haco, Linhas Círculo, Cremer, Artex, and Sulfabril between 1920 and 1940, during which the number of textile workers rose from 1,344 to 4,972 (FIESC, 2010). All of these companies became large players in their respective specialties.

Indeed, the context of World War I was very favorable to industries in Santa Catarina as well as generally throughout Brazil. It enabled the emergence of coal production in Santa Catarina and Rio Grande do Sul. The major shipowner from Rio de Janeiro, Henrique Lage (Cia de Navegação Costeira), became highly vulnerable to the decline in imports of English steam coal, necessary for the boilers of his ships, and thus heavily invested in opening mines, beginning commercial production in 1917. After the war, the situation became critical due to the resumption of English imports, but the government resulting from the 1930 Revolution, strongly nationalist, established a mandatory consumption of 10% national coal in 1931, raised to 20% in 1937, guaranteeing the profitability of the business. World War II allowed further import substitutions in the coal sector, with extraction increasingly carried out by local contractors such as S. Guglielmi and D. Freitas, who ended up creating powerful companies. The start of operations of the Companhia Siderúrgica Nacional (CSN) in 1945 granted Santa Catarina exclusivity in the national coke coal market, leading to the establishment of a CSN mining subsidiary (Cia Próspera), which later began to channel its steam coal production to a 25,000 kW thermoelectric power plant near the city of Tubarão, along the railway line to the coal port of Imbituba.

The third major industrial region of Santa Catarina is the West, where a strong system of integration and entrapment of settlers by slaughterhouses (pork, chicken, turkey, etc.) developed. This is the most complete case of agro-industry in southern Brazil, where several small and medium-sized businesses emerged that ultimately led to increasing concentration in the hands of three large groups: Sadia, Perdigão, and Seara. In recent decades, the growth of cooperativism in that region gave rise to the large Aurora group. The pork slaughterhouses appeared in the 1930s and 1940s as an extension of two activities: a) commercial, involving buying from small settlers and selling pigs to the large slaughterhouses in São Paulo, such as Swift and Armour; b) meat processing, which already existed in the Itajaí Valley and especially in northern Rio Grande do Sul, from where settlers and small merchants like Atilio Fontana and Saul Brandalise arrived, who founded Sadia and Perdigão, which from the start had access to the rapidly expanding São Paulo market. The integration mentioned above accelerated with the establishment in the 1960s of modern chicken slaughterhouses aimed at retaining settlers with small land holdings in the region while at the same time gaining new markets.

Just as the industries established by Germans competed with and conquered the markets of São Paulo firms in knitwear, terry cloth towels, and other fabrics, the slaughterhouses in the West also competed with and surpassed the Rio Grande do Sul firms, thanks to their better location and cheaper raw materials. They also pushed Minas Gerais out of the São Paulo market by replacing lard supply with more refined cured meats. Internships at slaughterhouses in Italy, Denmark, and the United States were key to production improvements. In the post-World War II period, Sadia and Perdigão benefited from DC-3 airplanes—surplus from the U.S. war effort—which were used and inexpensive, allowing faster transport of cured meats to the São Paulo market and others, thus giving rise to airlines like Transbrasil.

Distant from the consumer market, companies in Santa Catarina generally had to constantly improve themselves, renewing machinery and work methods, training the workforce, and reducing costs. They benefited from favorable labor relations, as the work ethic of Italian and German settlers was passed down to their children and grandchildren, the workers. Therefore, it is not surprising that Artex was a pioneer in textile exports to the United States in 1958. With the crisis of 1962-65, the Blumenau-based company expanded its presence, created its own trading company, and opened the way for exports from other Santa Catarina firms, such as Hering, Teka, Karsten, among others.

Statistical data (Table 1) clearly show the dynamism of Santa Catarina's industry in the period from 1940 to 1980. In 1940, Santa Catarina accounted for only 1.8% of Brazil's industrial production value (with 2.9% of the population), rising to 2.0% in 1950, reaching 2.1% in 1960, 2.6% in 1970, and 3.9% in 1980 (3.0% of the population), which represented extraordinary growth during 1970-80, well above the national average. According to B. W. Werner (1985), Santa Catarina's industry grew at an

average annual rate of 14.7% during 1970-78, amid the “Brazilian miracle,” largely driven by state exports, which increased from US\$77 million in 1972 to US\$529 million in 1979, mostly manufactured goods. Thus, it is not surprising that Santa Catarina’s per capita income of US\$1,044 in 1970 reached US\$2,555 in 1980 and continued to grow. In 2007, Santa Catarina recorded the 2nd highest industrial GDP per capita in Brazil, behind only São Paulo. In 1985, Santa Catarina’s GDP was distributed as 16% in the primary sector, 37.9% in the secondary (industry) sector, and 46.1% in the tertiary sector, shifting to 7.2% in agriculture and livestock, 35.7% in industry, and 57.1% in commerce and services by 2007 (FIESC, 2010).

Table 1 – Industrial and Population Shares of States in the Total Brazilian Percentage (%) – IBGE

	1940		1980		2000		2010		2021	
	Ind.	pop.								
São Paulo	43,5	17,4	52,8	21,0	45,3	21,8	38,9	21,6	31,5	21,0
Minas Gerais	6,7	16,4	8,6	11,2	9,7	10,5	10,4	10,3	12,1	9,6
Rio Grande do Sul	9,8	8,1	7,1	6,5	9,1	6,0	8,4	5,6	7,8	5,1
Rio de Janeiro	23,9	8,8	10,3	9,5	7,3	8,5	7,9	8,4	8,3	7,5
Paraná	2,1	3,0	5,0	6,4	6,4	5,6	7,6	5,5	7,9	5,4
Santa Catarina	1,8	2,9	4,0	3,0	4,4	3,2	4,7	3,3	5,9	3,6
Bahia	1,4	9,5	3,4	7,9	3,9	7,7	4,4	7,4	3,6	6,6

Source: Adapted by the authors. Mamigonian (2011) IBGE (2021).

By 1980, Santa Catarina was already proportionally more industrialized than Paraná and Rio Grande do Sul, where the standout business groups were Bamerindus and CR Almeida, in heavy engineering in the former case, and VARIG and the Gerdau group in the latter. Meanwhile, the economic groups in Santa Catarina, smaller than those in the neighboring states, were industrial and spread throughout the territory: 1) Hering, Artex, Tupy, Tigre, WEG in the German-settled areas; 2) Sadia and Perdigão in the West; 3) Guglielmi, Freitas, and Gaidzinski in the South, in addition to the state-owned companies for electricity generation (Eletrosul) and transmission (Celesc), as well as ICC carbo-chemicals and groups from São Paulo (Klabin, Brastemp, etc.). However, it should be noted that this almost “idyllic” picture of Santa Catarina in 1980 changed with the destructive trade opening of the 1990s. By 2000, several Santa

Catarina companies had left family control: out of the 23 largest companies in the state, only 11 remained under Santa Catarina management, 7 belonged to foreign groups, 3 to pension funds, and 2 to national groups.

As emphasized earlier, Santa Catarina, like the entire South of Brazil, moved from a peripheral condition to become part of the dynamic core of the Brazilian economy. This occurred between the 1970s and 1980s, not only due to the size reached by the mechanical and electrical sectors but also because of the national leadership positions assumed by its main companies. The electromechanical sector in the German-settled area reached national and even international scale. The Consul industry in Joinville, for example, began producing refrigerators for rural areas without electricity and gradually advanced to making sophisticated refrigerators, growing from 3 to 5% of the national market in the 1950s to achieving leadership with over 30% in 1975-80, surpassing GE, Frigidaire (GM), and others located in São Paulo. It started exporting to South America, began producing air-conditioning units, and established Embraco, a compressor factory, among others. It is worth noting that after this bold and successful trajectory, the Freitag group paid the price for its dynamism, lacking necessary government support, and disappeared, reduced to its original appliance stores. After passing through the hands of the Brastemp group from São Paulo, Consul and Embraco ended up in the hands of the American Whirlpool group, one of the largest in the world in the sector.

Besides Consul, which belonged to the Joinville-based Freitag group, whose history was summarized above, the German-settled areas gave rise to many other dynamic companies such as the foundry Tupy, WEG, Eletroação Altona, and others in the electrical and metal-mechanical sectors. Not to mention the vast textile and garment industries of Blumenau, Brusque, Joinville, and other cities, which also demonstrated significant dynamism, conquered the national market, and ventured into exports.

4. Notes on the advances and setbacks of the industrial region of german origin

In the northeast of Santa Catarina—from Joinville to Rio Negrinho in the Northern Plateau, and from there to Rio do Sul in the Upper Itajaí Valley, continuing toward Brusque in the Itajaí-Mirim Valley, then on to Blumenau and back to Joinville, forming the perimeter of the most industrialized area—this region, encompassing more than twenty municipalities, accounted for over 50.0% of Santa Catarina's total industrial output, and an even larger proportion of the state's manufacturing value. Within this area, two industrial centers stood out: Joinville with 19.5% and Blumenau with 17.4% of the state's industrial production in 1980. In this industrial region, the secondary sector employed more than 50.0% of the total workforce, and in no municipality was that figure below 30.0%. In fact, it reached 55.0% in Blumenau and 58.0% in Joinville, exceeding or approaching 66.0% in several municipalities (such as Pomerode, Guabiruba, Rio Negrinho, and São Bento do Sul). To summarize, this region alone produced no less than 2.1% of Brazil's industrial value in 1980, despite accounting for

only 0.7% of the national population—meaning it was three times more industrialized than the national average.

In its early days, the German-origin region had a very modest economic life. The first artisanal-manufactured exports from the region were small amounts of lard, dairy products, and timber destined for the domestic market, and small quantities of cigars, tobacco, and wood shipped to Europe. These exports remained dominant until World War I, when textile industries—emerging around 1880—began to capture the domestic market, substituting imports and remaining the leading industrial sector until approximately 1950.

The mechanical workshops and foundries, numerous in the early stages of small-scale mercantile production in Blumenau, Brusque, and Joinville, were able to expand in the latter city, as they were called upon to serve: 1) the railway branch line connecting the port of São Francisco to the junction at Porto União; 2) the maintenance of marine engines of ships docking at São Francisco do Sul; 3) the transport wagons carrying erva-mate from the Plateau to Joinville; 4) the needs of sawmills and timber industries linked to the exploitation of the Atlantic Forest and the pinewoods of the Plateau; 5) the needs of settlers and emerging small industries. This early metal-mechanical development explains why Otto Bennack became a pioneer in Brazil in the production of metal lathes before World War II, an initiative that was later discontinued (Rocha, 1997).

Both the small industries of Blumenau and its surroundings, as well as those of Joinville and neighboring areas, although modest, were founded on solid ground and expanded rapidly. Hering, for example, which operated as a craft-based, family-run business from 1880 to 1895, became, during World War I, the largest knitwear manufacturer in Brazil. By 1960, it had reached a total of 1,800 employees and went on to become, in the 1970s, one of Brazil's major industrial groups, employing over 23,000 workers by 1980. While major industrial groups in the Northeast—such as Lundgren and Othon Bezerra de Mello—declined, the Hering Group encompassed: 1) the largest knitwear manufacturer in the world (16,000 employees); 2) the largest soybean oil processor in Brazil (Ceval); 3) the third-largest producer of pork and poultry in Brazil (Seara), in addition to its presence in telecommunications equipment, through a partnership with Siemens in Curitiba, as well as hotels and retail stores in Santa Catarina, spinning and knitwear operations in Recife, etc. (Cia Hering, 1980). At its main knitwear plant, productivity rose steadily: in 1915, one worker produced 127 dozen pieces (38,000 in total), in 1965, 427 dozen (800,000), reaching 1,110 dozen in 1980 (12 million), without proportional increases in workers' wages (Renaux Hering, 1985).

Between 1940 and 1980, the greatest growth in Brazil's textile sector occurred in Santa Catarina, which accounted for 8.7% of national textile production and 9.3% of garment manufacturing by 1980. Out of the US\$ 1 billion exported by the Santa

Catarina economy in 1985, textiles represented US\$ 103 million, a significant share of Brazil's total textile exports. However, in the 1990s, the situation in both the Brazilian and Santa Catarina textile sectors changed radically: 1) due to the invasion of the domestic market by Asian products, with imports jumping from US\$ 535 million in 1992 to US\$ 2.4 billion in 1997; and 2) due to the challenges faced by Brazilian exports, which had reached a level of US\$ 1.4 billion in 1994–95, but dropped to US\$ 1.1 billion in 1998–99, owing to the overvaluation of the real against the dollar.

The textile and apparel sector was the most affected industrial sector in Santa Catarina during the trade liberalization process: the reduction in import tariffs from 105% in 1990 to 20% in 1993, along with the overvalued exchange rate under the Real Plan, led to a flood of foreign products and a drop in the state's textile exports, from US\$ 423.6 million in 1993 (30.6% of Brazil's total) to US\$ 258.7 million in 1999 (26.6% of the total), according to (FIESC, 2010, p. 61). All of this happened despite the support of Governor Kleinubing, who pressured the federal government to raise import tariffs on Asian goods, giving Santa Catarina's industry a temporary reprieve.

Since 2004–05, with the increasingly cheap dollar, it became advantageous to import raw materials, semi-finished and even finished goods from Asia, while the strengthening of the real made exports of finished products unfeasible. As a result, Santa Catarina's textile and apparel firms began increasing the import content of their products and, unable to export them, turned to strengthening their presence in the domestic market, investing in branding, design, and franchised retail networks.

Indeed, a brilliant example of industrial enterprise from Joinville is the case of Tigre (Hansen Group), the largest national producer of rigid PVC pipes and fittings, with several factories in Brazil—in Rio Claro (SP) and Camaçari (BA)—as well as units in Paraguay and Argentina. Throughout its history, it has faced various challenges, such as the importation of petrochemical inputs during the 1973–74 oil crisis, which it managed very well. Tigre continues to dominate the rigid PVC pipe and fittings market, even in the face of competition from Fortilit, a multinational owned by the Swiss group Amanco (now acquired by the Mexican petrochemical group Mexichem), which benefited from the economic crises that have affected Brazil and acquired the PVC division of the Tupy group and Akros, a company founded by former Tigre employees.

In the metal-mechanical and electrical sectors of the German-colonized regions of northeastern Santa Catarina, there are numerous examples of both dynamism and structural bottlenecks. As mentioned above, the Consul–Embraco group illustrates one such case, and many others demonstrate similar success. One of the most prominent examples is WEG Equipamentos Elétricos S.A., which employs more than 18,000 workers between Jaraguá do Sul and Blumenau, and reported R\$ 32 billion in revenue in 2023. WEG is the largest national company in its field, with industrial units in Argentina, Colombia, Mexico, the United States, Portugal, Spain, Italy, Germany,

Austria, India, and China, competing in the global market against multinational corporations in its area of operation.

Interestingly, more than half of WEG's revenue comes from the international market, through the manufacturing of electric motors, large-scale energy generation equipment, and a wide range of industrial products. It holds 45% of the North American market, directly competing with major U.S. conglomerates like General Electric, Emerson Electric, and Rockwell Automation. In Europe, it generates 26% of its international revenue, directly competing with Siemens (Germany), Schneider Electric (France), and ABB (Switzerland). Meanwhile, it has been expanding its market in Asia, which now represents 8% of its revenue, where it competes directly with Mitsubishi Electric (Japan) and Wolong Electric (China).

Today, this Brazilian company, which has a global presence with 52 manufacturing plants spread across 15 countries, approximately 40,000 employees, and 5,000 engineers, ranks as the 3rd most valuable company in Brazil (market value – R\$223.4 billion), behind only Petrobras and Itaú-Unibanco. In fact, the company currently holds the 5th position in the ranking of electric motors in Asia and the Pacific, behind ABB, Siemens, Toshiba, and Nidec, and ranks 4th in alternating current motors; in Africa and the Middle East, with the production of starter motors, it is in 3rd place, behind Eaton and Emerson, and in North America, it is positioned 2nd in the production of induction motors, only behind Schneider Electric.

WEG was founded in Jaraguá do Sul in 1961 by three partners and three employees, when it produced its first 146 small electric motors, following the example of Kohlbach, which had started a few years earlier. By 1965, WEG employed 100 workers, produced 9,000 motors, covered the entire South of Brazil, and penetrated directly into the interior of São Paulo, bypassing wholesalers in the São Paulo capital. Secretly seeking technology in São Paulo, where its giant competitors such as Arno, GE, Buffalo, and Motores Brasil were located, the Santa Catarina company accelerated its growth at an annual rate of 37% during the 1965–75 decade. By 1975, it employed 1,550 people, produced 308,000 motors, and became the largest producer in Latin America, where it had started exporting in 1970. Exports gradually reached the entire world, and production reached 994,000 motors in 1981, dropping to 621,000 in 1983 during that period of crisis, but by 1985 it had already reached 1,035,000 motors.

At the end of the 1970s, the company felt the need to diversify, creating WEG-Drives, which produces electronic components and programmable controllers—an advanced area competing with Romi, Mangels, and other São Paulo-based producers—and also WEG-Machines, which manufactures electrical equipment for mining, petrochemical, pulp and paper industries, etc. During the 1981–82 crisis, it acquired a transformer factory in Blumenau, which became WEG-Transformers, as well as WEG-Chemicals in Guaramirim, which produces not only for its own needs but also paints for automotive manufacturers, in addition to

WEG-Fisheries (Penha). The company also applied tax incentives in WEG-Reforestation in the municipalities of Corupá, São Bento do Sul, and Araquari, totaling 4,500 hectares by 1995 (Ternes, 1997).

The metal-mechanical industry in the German-settled areas of Santa Catarina presents numerous other examples of dynamic companies such as the Tupy foundry, Metisa – a metallurgical company from Timbó, Docol sanitary metals, Carlos Schneider Industrial Company, Schulz, among others. The Tupy foundry had a revenue of R\$ 1.4 billion, producing, since its beginnings in 1938, not only cast iron fittings—a sector in which it dominates the Brazilian market—but also auto parts like engine blocks and cylinder heads, using vermicular technology, supplying the national market as well as exporting to luxury automobile groups such as Jaguar, Audi, and others, ranking 5th worldwide in the machining sector.

The bold advancement of Santa Catarina's industries starts from a geographically disadvantaged position, with raw materials and consumer markets distant—similar to Sweden's position relative to Europe and Japan's to the world—compensated, as in those countries, by the compulsory competition that leads to a permanent struggle for technological progress. This is supported not only by internal research centers within companies (WEG, Tupy, Eletroação Altona, etc.) but also by research centers abroad, equipped not only with sophisticated experimental equipment but also with software for electromagnetic field calculation that WEG acquired at UFSC, engineers with specialized training, a library of international scientific journals, frequent participation in world fairs of their sectors aiming at absorbing technology from the most advanced competitors, in addition to research contracts with leading universities in Brazil and abroad (Hannover, for example). Beyond all this, companies must plan vertical integration whenever necessary, as well as product diversification to ensure financial balance.

Despite everything mentioned, companies of German origin in Santa Catarina, as was the case in the textile sector, had to face the neoliberal challenge of the 1990s and the absence of a dynamic industrial policy by successive Brazilian governments. Thus, besides the loss of controlling shares of Artex, Sulfabril, Buettner, the best-known cases in Joinville were those of Consul-Embraco and Tupy, the latter currently controlled by Previ-Bradesco.

In summary, despite the enormous expansion in the 1970s and 1980s in knitwear, terry cloth, glassware, porcelain, refrigerators, etc. in the consumer goods sector, and varied production in the capital goods sector such as motors, woodworking machines, numerical controls, auto parts, castings, general steel products, compressors, bus bodies, plastics for sanitation, all competing successfully in national and international markets, all these sectors have lacked a correct industrial policy since 1990.

5. Final remarks

The industrial sector of Santa Catarina, like Brazilian industry as a whole, grew from 1880 to 1930 under the aegis of power pacts that encompassed export-import commercial capital and the landowning elite—enslavers until 1888 and feudal landlords thereafter. From 1930 to 1990, it grew under the nationalist pact, victorious with the 1930 Revolution, which included the industrial bourgeoisie as a partner, though still under the command of the feudal landowning class oriented toward the domestic market. The counter-revolution of the 1990s, inspired by U.S. imperialism and whose remnants persist to this day, turned against Brazilian industry, which remains heavily penalized.

The industrialization of Santa Catarina and the resulting industry constitute very rich and fascinating topics in economic and social history and geography. It emerged during the global depression of 1873–1896, a period that saw the gestation of imperialism by dominant countries, such as the expansion of the French and British empires, as well as the advances of the Second Industrial Revolution (electricity, internal combustion engine, assembly line, etc.) led by Germany and the USA. The contraction of international trade during this period, along with rising import taxes in Brazil, was significant for the founding of Hering in Blumenau and Dohler in Joinville in 1880, aimed at serving newly settled German colonists. These companies were tiny compared to the large textile factories established around the same time in São Luís do Maranhão, Recife, Salvador, Rio de Janeiro, Rio Grande, and other cities, which were backed by the large commercial capitals controlling those ports. Hering, Dohler, and a few others demonstrated remarkable vitality, growing steadily and surviving the neoliberal opening of recent decades, while those late-19th-century factories (such as Lundgren, Bangu, Rheingantz, etc.) long ago closed their doors, including the largest Brazilian industrial group of the mid-20th century, Matarazzo.

Historically, attention should be drawn to the protectionist circumstances created by the world wars, as in the case of coal, whose production began during the First World War and received a significant boost during the Second. The industries in the German-colonized areas were also favored by these circumstances and benefited after the conflicts ended from the immigration of numerous potential entrepreneurs and technicians born in Germany. Examples include O. Klimeck, a Spartacist revolutionary who, in the 1920s, founded Condor S.A. in São Bento do Sul, producing brushes, brooms, and other items, currently employing 1,000 workers; and a former German army officer who, after the Second World War, together with his wife, established Ceramarte Ltda in Rio Negrinho, manufacturing ceramic beer mugs and other products, employing 450 people as of 2009.

In the process of import substitution that characterized Brazilian industrialization, Santa Catarina's participation was consistently active. This was evident in the first wave of substitution of basic consumer goods such as textiles and

processed foods (like cured meats and dairy products from the Itajaí Valley in the early 20th century). This process was further strengthened in the textile sector with more refined items such as quilts by Altenburg, terry towels by Artex, and curtains by Buettner. By the 1930s, Santa Catarina had also made its presence felt in the second level of import substitution—intermediate consumer goods—such as tiles from Cerâmica Santa Catarina in Imbituba and malleable iron fittings from Fundação Tupy. There were also efforts to establish cement factories, like the one planned (but never realized) by C. Renaux, a pioneer of the textile industry in Brusque. Naturally, Santa Catarina had little opportunity to participate in the third level of substitution, which involved heavy inputs like steel and oil—except for Eletroação Altona in Blumenau. However, it had a strong presence in the substitution of durable consumer goods such as refrigerators, air conditioners, washing machines, and so on, as well as in the next stage of heavy mechanical and electrical equipment, particularly through WEG, thus both accompanying and accelerating Brazilian industrialization.

With the victory of the 1930 Revolution, in Santa Catarina the state leadership shifted from politicians linked to export-import trade (Konder, Luz, and others) to leaders from the Planalto of Lages, such as Nereu Ramos and his family, who were committed to the nationalist economic policy initiated by Getúlio Vargas. Consequently, both in Brazil and in Santa Catarina from 1930 to 1990, measures were gradually implemented to stimulate industrial growth, such as mandatory consumption of domestic coal (10% in 1931 and 20% in 1937) and state investments in energy, road, and port sectors. In Santa Catarina, initiatives like Procape allowed tax deductions for industries to encourage the establishment of new factories, while at the national level, several measures supported industry, such as the machine renewal policy for exporting industries through the draw-back system.

The minor currency devaluations in the early 1980s, led by Delfim Netto, aimed to take advantage of idle production capacities, increased by the 1979–1980 crisis, and accelerated exports, allowing companies such as Dohler to enter the textile export market, Zen to expand auto parts exports, and WEG to increase its exports, among others. Santa Catarina's export potential had already been demonstrated, with a leap from US\$77 million in 1972 to US\$529 million in 1979. The last major industrial policy was the computer market reserve, which gave rise to the successful Itautec experience and facilitated the emergence of the high-tech sector in Florianópolis and other cities in Santa Catarina.

It should be noted that the success of the high-tech sector in Florianópolis, and also in Blumenau (Sênior Sistemas) and Joinville (Datasul), was based in part on the availability of strong mechanical and electrical engineering courses at UFSC, which formed an early partnership with the Santa Catarina industry since the 1960s (Cônsul, WEG, etc.), further strengthened by the presence of Telesc, part of the Telebrás system, which used fiber optics in telecommunications during the 1970s when this technology was just beginning to be deployed in the U.S. and Japan.

Unfortunately, after the neoliberal opening of the 1990s, the situation changed, with a disconnection between federal and state economic policies and the interests of industries in Santa Catarina and Brazil. In the case of the Santa Catarina Technological Hub, now ParqTec Alfa, the initial project by the state government aimed to attract U.S. companies—which did not come—and later companies from São Paulo, which also did not arrive. The government failed to recognize the real and dynamic presence of Florianópolis-based companies, such as Dígito and others, which were competing in a market harmed by predatory trade liberalization. The disconnection between federal and state economic policies and industrial interests became evident more recently with the reduction of the state ICM tax rate on imported products, from 17% to 3%, detrimental to most Santa Catarina and Brazilian industries but favoring the “movement” of Santa Catarina ports.

Given the remarkable entrepreneurial dynamism in Santa Catarina, it should come as no surprise that the state holds a significant position in various industrial sectors in Brazil. As of 2021, with Santa Catarina accounting for 5.9% of the national industrial output, its share is especially noteworthy in sectors such as machinery and equipment manufacturing (7.1%), metal-mechanical and metallurgy (10.9%), electrical equipment (9.6%), as well as in lower value-added sectors such as food and beverages (26.4%), textile manufacturing (12.1%), furniture production (5.8%), plastic and chemical materials (9.6%), and ceramics (3.9%). Unfortunately, due to the absence of a coherent national industrial policy, many of the major companies operating in Santa Catarina have left the hands of their pioneering founders and are now controlled by pension funds or multinational corporations.

On the other hand, Santa Catarina, even occupying 6th place with 5.9% of national industrial output (2021), proved to be the most industrially dynamic state, having increased its absolute share by 213% over the decade 2011–2021, followed by Paraná with 165% and Rio Grande do Sul with 150% (Table 1).

It is worth noting that this industrial dynamism in Santa Catarina is reflected in the regional diversification of industry (27.5% of the state GDP), although the Itajaí Valley and Northern Santa Catarina stand out due to higher population concentrations (45.5%), with a strong urban agglomeration in which highly technologically sophisticated industrial and logistics sectors are concentrated in the cities of Joinville, Blumenau, and Jaraguá do Sul, representing “23.3% of the state’s industrial GDP” (Instituto Euvaldo Lodi de Santa Catarina, 2022, p.27).

Interestingly, among the three most industrialized cities mentioned, Jaraguá do Sul in 2022 stood out as the city where the industrial sector predominates (45.12%), followed by Joinville (35.47%) and Blumenau (27.19%) (FIESC, 2024a). This is further reflected in employment by economic sector: Jaraguá do Sul has the majority of its jobs in industry, with 52.39%, while Joinville has 36.21% and Blumenau 35.06%.

However, when considering population data, it is notable that in the urban hierarchy, Jaraguá do Sul is a typical medium-sized city (184,579 inhabitants), smaller than Blumenau (366,418 inhabitants) and Joinville (604,708 inhabitants). Regarding formal direct employment in 2022, these cities had 74,215, 144,608, and 232,931 jobs, respectively. Jaraguá do Sul has a per capita GDP (R\$65,295) higher than Blumenau (R\$56,155) but lower than Joinville (R\$74,531), the most populous city in Santa Catarina (FIESC, 2024a).

Furthermore, considering indicators of wealth concentration and inequality, Santa Catarina ranks as the most balanced state in Brazil, with a Gini coefficient of 0.418—the lowest in the 2023 series.

Focusing on average income, Jaraguá do Sul stands out among the three industrial cities as the 4th highest in Santa Catarina (R\$2,392.79), behind Florianópolis, Joaçaba, and Balneário Camboriú, and ahead of Blumenau, 5th (R\$2,269.16), and Joinville, 8th (R\$1,990.80). Even in terms of the average income of tax filers and their average net wealth, Jaraguá do Sul recorded higher indicators in 2020 (R\$9,552.67 / R\$449,234.12) than Joinville (R\$8,031.21 / R\$275,813.11) and Blumenau (R\$8,523.27 / R\$344,457.80) (FGV Social/CPS, 2020).

Moreover, while Santa Catarina's overall trade balance remained in deficit in the last three years, Jaraguá do Sul maintained a surplus of R\$292.21 million in 2023, with exports exceeding imports, driven primarily by the electrical equipment sector, which accounted for 66.68% of exports (FIESC, 2024b).

Currently, the electrical equipment sector in Jaraguá do Sul ranks 2nd in formal job creation, employing 11,150 workers, 95.13% of whom are in large companies (FIESC, 2024c), such as WEG. Today, this Brazilian company has a global presence with 52 manufacturing plants across 15 countries, around 40,000 employees, and 5,000 engineers, ranking as the 3rd most valuable company in Brazil (market value – R\$223.4 billion), only behind Petrobras and Itaú-Unibanco, with revenue reaching R\$38 billion in 2024.

Interestingly, more than half of WEG's revenue is generated in international markets, producing electric motors, large energy generation equipment, and a range of industrial products. WEG holds 45% of the North American market, competing directly with U.S. conglomerates such as General Electric, Emerson Electric, and Rockwell Automation; in Europe, it earns 26% of its international revenue, competing with Siemens (Germany), Schneider Electric (France), and ABB (Switzerland); and in Asia, it accounts for 8% of revenue, competing with Mitsubishi Electric (Japan) and Wolong Electric (China).

In short, WEG currently ranks 5th in the electric motor market in Asia and the Pacific, behind ABB, Siemens, Toshiba, and Nidec, and 4th in alternating current motors; in Africa and the Middle East, producing starter motors, it ranks 3rd, behind

Eaton and Emerson; in North America, it ranks 2nd in induction motor production, only behind Schneider Electric.

Finally, despite the enormous potential generated by WEG's electrical equipment production in Jaraguá do Sul and worldwide, it is important not to overlook the role of the large textile sector (textiles, clothing, footwear, leather, etc.), which still plays a major role in the city. The textile sector remains the main source of employment in Jaraguá do Sul, providing 13,879 jobs concentrated in large companies such as Malwee, Marisol, Lunelli, and Live, forming a significant regional cluster integrated into the national market.

It appears, and this will be further explored in subsequent research, that the process of Brazilian deindustrialization in recent decades, although penalizing the thriving textile sector of the Itajaí Valley, did not result in deindustrialization in the northeastern region of Santa Catarina. The relocation of the textile sector along with the metal-mechanical and electrical materials industries to this region shows that, according to the data, industrial activity has remained robust there.

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